

Greenhouse Gas Emissions from a Tropical Eutrophic Freshwater Wetland

Juan P. Silva, T. R. Canchala, H. J. Lubberding, E. J. Peña, H. J. Gijzen

Abstract—This study measured the fluxes of greenhouse gases (GHGs) i.e. CO₂, CH₄ and N₂O from a tropical eutrophic freshwater wetland (“Sonso Lagoon”) which receives input loading nutrient from several sources i.e. agricultural run-off, domestic sewage, and a polluted river. The flux measurements were carried out at four different points using the static chamber technique. CO₂ fluxes ranged from -8270 to 12210 mg.m⁻².d⁻¹ (median = 360; SD = 4.11; n = 50), CH₄ ranged between 0.2 and 5270 mg.m⁻².d⁻¹ (median = 60; SD = 1.27; n = 45), and N₂O ranged from -31.12 to 15.4 mg N₂O m⁻².d⁻¹ (median = 0.05; SD = 9.36; n = 42). Although some negative fluxes were observed in the zone dominated by floating plants i.e. *Eichornia crassipes*, *Salvinia* sp., and *Pistia stratiotes* L., the mean values indicated that the Sonso Lagoon was a net source of CO₂, CH₄ and N₂O. In addition, an effect of the eutrophication on GHG emissions could be observed in the positive correlation found between CO₂, CH₄ and N₂O generation and COD, PO₄⁻³, NH₃-N, TN and NO₃-N. The eutrophication impact on GHG production highlights the necessity to limit the anthropic activities on freshwater wetlands.

Keywords—Eutrophication, greenhouse gas emissions, freshwater wetlands, climate change.

I. INTRODUCTION

FRESHWATER Wetlands (FW) provide ecosystem services such as water purification, flood control, nutrient cycling, carbon sequestration, foods, maintenance of biodiversity and climate regulation [1], [2]. By contrast, FWs can be an important source of GHGs and it has been estimated that CH₄ emissions from tropical wetlands are 128 Tg.yr⁻¹ and equivalent to 75% of the total emissions from wetlands worldwide [3]. Wetlands can also emit between 0.01 and 1% of N₂O and 0.648-9.18 Tg C (CO₂) [4], whereas the global CO₂ evasion rates are 1800 Tg C.yr⁻¹ from streams and rivers and 320 Tg C. yr⁻¹ from lakes [5]. These emissions can be even higher where wetlands have been affected by anthropogenic activities such as agricultural run-off and domestic sewage discharges. These activities provide input loading nutrients (N and P) and organic matter to FW, resulting in a severe alteration of the structure and function by eutrophication of these ecosystems [4]. Eutrophication in FW generally promotes excessive algae and plant growth and

Juan P. Silva is with the Universidad del Valle, Cali, Colombia. Street 13 No 100-00 Melendez Campus (phone: +57 23398560; e-mail: juan.silva@correounivalle.edu.co).

T.R Canchala and E. J. Peña are with the Universidad del Valle, Cali, Colombia. Street 13 100-00 Melendez Campus (e-mail: teresita.canchala@correounivalle.edu.co, enrique.peña@correounivalle.edu.co).

H. J. Lubberding is with UNESCO – IHE Institute for Water Education, Westvest 7, 2611 AX Delft, Netherlands (e-mail: waglub@xs4all.nl).

H. J. Gijzen is with UNESCO Regional Office for Southern Africa, Harare, Zimbabwe. (e-mail: h.gijzen@unesco.org).

decay, favouring simple algae and plankton over other more complicated plants, and this causes a severe reduction in water quality i.e. oxygen depletion [6]. In addition, the nutrient loading enhances organic matter decomposition and microbial activity [7], which may lead to increased accumulation of carbon and nitrogen. So eutrophication affects the FW biogeochemistry, leading to acceleration of the exchange of GHGs between FWs and the atmosphere [8], [9].

Several authors have shown that freshwater ecosystems under eutrophication or with excessive loading nutrients are important sources of GHGs [8], [10]-[16]. Since these studies were carried out under temperate and subtropical conditions it is important to study whether the GHG emissions from these wetlands are comparable to those under tropical conditions and also whether the variables mentioned influence their GHG production.

In Colombia, approximately 20,000,000 hectares are classified as wetland and most of these wetlands are eutrophic. As a consequence, the GHG emissions are increasing. Because the impact of eutrophication on GHG emissions in tropical eutrophic wetlands is still unclear and there are many uncertainties about the magnitude of these GHG emissions, in this study we focus on (1) the quantification of CH₄, CO₂, and N₂O and (2) the identification of the factors that regulate the emissions of CH₄, CO₂, and N₂O from an eutrophic tropical FW.

II. MATERIAL AND METHODS

A. Study Area

The Sonso Lagoon (3°51'43.36" N and 76°20'57.12" W) is a shallow eutrophic lake. It is located in the southwestern part of Colombia, on the right bank of the Cauca River. The total area of the Sonso Lagoon is 20.5 km² of which 7.5 km² are water mirror and 13 km² riparian buffer zones. It has a mean depth of 1.6 m with a maximum depth of 3 m. The climate is tropical with a mean annual temperature ranging from 21 to 26°C and 1,375 mm precipitation yearly. The Sonso Lagoon exchanges water and sediments with the regional Cauca River through the Caño Nuevo Channel (Fig. 1). This river is characterized by high pollution due to industrial effluents. In addition, there are inlets of domestic sewage and agricultural runoff from sugar cane crops into the lake. Through these discharges, organic matter, nitrogen compounds, phosphorus compounds, heavy metals, pesticides and herbicides enter the lagoon affecting its water characteristics.

The four study sites in the Sonso Lagoon were as follows (Fig. 1): P1, exchange zone of water and sediments with the

Cauca River; P2, zone dominated by domestic sewage and agricultural runoff discharges; P3, dominated by phytoplankton; P4, dominated by water hyacinths.

Fig. 1 Location of the Sonso Lagoon and sampling points for measurements of GHG emissions

B. Water Characteristics

Environmental data from the four sites of the Sonso Lagoon were collected to determine the water quality and to evaluate the relationship between GHGs and environmental parameters. The measurements of environmental data were carried out between 9 am and 3 pm, which coincided with the GHG emission measurements. Chemical oxygen demand (COD), total suspended solids (TSS), alkalinity, total Kjeldahl nitrogen (TKN), ammonium nitrogen ($\text{NH}_4^+\text{-N}$), and nitrate nitrogen ($\text{NO}_3^-\text{-N}$) were measured according to Standard Methods [17]. Conductivity, pH, dissolved oxygen (DO), temperature and oxidation-reduction potential were measured with electrodes.

C. GHG Measurements

Emissions of CH_4 , CO_2 and N_2O were estimated with the static chamber technique [18]. The static chambers were of propylene and cylindrical (Diameter 0.43 m and Height 0.26 m). The chambers were equipped with a sampling port having a rubber septum from which the gas sample was taken.

During measurements, the chambers were installed gently on the water surface of each point. The gas samples were taken at regular time intervals of 10 minutes (0, 10, 20 and 30 minutes). The sample was extracted by a 20 mL syringe, which was inserted at the point of making the chamber (rubber septum), after which the sample was removed and injected into a previously sealed vial and vacuum 10 ml.

The Flux of CH_4 , CO_2 and N_2O were calculated according to the equation 1 from linear and no linear changes in the gas concentrations in the chamber headspaces [18].

$$F = \frac{dC}{dt_{t=0}} \times \frac{V_c}{A} \times \frac{1440 \text{ min}}{d} \quad (1)$$

F= Flux of CH_4 , CO_2 y N_2O ($\text{g}\cdot\text{m}^{-2}\cdot\text{d}^{-1}$); $dC/dt_{t=0}$ = Slope of the gas concentration curve ($\text{g}\cdot\text{m}^{-3}\cdot\text{d}^{-1}$); V_c = Volume of the chamber (m^3); A_c = The cross-sectional area of the chamber (m^2).

D. Gas Analysis

CH_4 was analyzed by gas chromatography (Shimadzu Co., Japan) equipped with a flame ionic detector (FID) and a Porapak Q column, and the temperature of the oven and injector ports were set at 60 and 80 °C, respectively. CO_2 was measured by an infrared spectrophotometer Qubit S151 CO_2 analyser (Loligo Systems, Denmark) using 75 ml min^{-1} air as the mobile phase with the temperature of the injector set equal to the ambient temperature. The N_2O concentration was analysed by means of gas chromatography (Shimadzu Co., Japan) equipped with an electron capture detector (ECD) and a Porapak column Q 80–100 mesh 2 m*2 mm retention gap, using 22 ml min^{-1} . N_2 was the carrier gas, and the injector, column, and detector temperatures were 80, 70, and 320 °C, respectively.

E. Data Analysis

Statistical analyses were done with SPSS® software (v. 17.0 for Windows). The Kolmogorov-Smirnov test was used to check the normality of the data. This normality check was done to determine whether parametric or non-parametric tests should be applied to analyse the data. To determine the differences in GHG fluxes from the different sample points, the Kruskal-Wallis and Mann Whitney non-parametric tests ($\alpha = 0.05$) were used. In addition, the relationship among the environmental data and GHG fluxes was estimated by using Spearman correlation coefficients.

III. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

A. Water Characteristics

TABLE I
WATER CHARACTERISTICS OF THE SONSO LAGOON (MEAN AND STANDARD DEVIATION ARE SHOWN)

Parameter	Sampling Point			
	P1	P2	P3	P4
Depth (m)	0.6±0.3	0.5±0.5	0.7±0.5	0.6±0.6
Water temperature (°C)	26.8±2.5	28.7±2.9	30.3±2.8	30.4±2.6
Water transparency (m)	0.1±0.1	0.1±0.1	0.1±0.1	0.2±0.1
pH (units)	7.8±0.5	7.8±0.4	7.9±0.4	7.8±0.5
Alkalinity (mg $\text{CaCO}_3\cdot\text{l}^{-1}$)	172.8±52.2	215.7±55	227.2±37	256.2±40
DO ($\text{mg}\cdot\text{l}^{-1}$)	4.4±2.2	4.5±1.7	5.4±1.6	4.6±1.6
COD ($\text{mg O}_2\cdot\text{l}^{-1}$)	33.8±9.5	31.6±12	31.7±12.3	32.1±12.2
TN ($\text{mg}\cdot\text{l}^{-1}$)	1.3±1.1	1.2±1.4	1.8±2.1	1.7±1.8
$\text{NH}_4^+\text{-N}$ ($\text{mg}\cdot\text{l}^{-1}$)	1.0±0.5	0.9±0.6	0.7±0.4	0.5±0.3
$\text{NO}_3^-\text{-N}$ ($\text{mg}\cdot\text{l}^{-1}$)	0.06±0.08	0.08±0.1	0.07±0.09	0.12±0.1
TP ($\text{mg}\cdot\text{l}^{-1}$)	0.17±0.11	0.31±0.15	0.24±0.08	0.08±0.1
$\text{PO}_4^{3-}\text{-P}$ ($\text{mg}\cdot\text{l}^{-1}$)	0.07±0.04	0.16±0.09	0.11±0.07	0.05±0.1

In Table I are shown the concentrations of dissolved oxygen (DO), total phosphorus (TP), and total nitrogen (TN) measured in the Sonso Lagoon. The DO concentrations

measured indicate that in the SL there was oxygen depletion for all the sampling points, thus OD values such as 4.4 mg.l⁻¹ were measured. The TN ranged from 1.2 to 1.8 mg.l⁻¹ while TP varied between 0.05 and 0.08 mg.l⁻¹ indicating nutrient excess. Also the transparency was lower than reported for non-eutrophic aquatic ecosystems. Further, COD ranged from 20 to 40 mg O₂.l⁻¹, which is above the values in water quality guides for freshwater (20 mg O₂.l⁻¹) [19].

The water characteristics measurements indicated that the Sonso Lagoon is eutrophic. This can be explained due to the input of organic matter and nutrients from the River Cauca, agricultural run-off, and domestic sewage discharges.

B. GHG Fluxes

Methane

The median methane fluxes for P1, P2, P3 and P4 were 0.037, 0.116, 0.078, and 0.059 g.m⁻².d⁻¹, respectively (Fig. 2). In general, P1, P2, P3 and P4 were net sources of methane. The only significant difference in flux was observed between P1 and P4 (p = 0.012).

Fig. 2 Flux of CH₄ in the Sonso Lagoon

TABLE II
SPEARMAN CORRELATIONS BETWEEN CH₄ FLUXES AND WATER CHARACTERISTICS

Parameter	P1	P2	P3	P4
DO	n.o	(0.048;-50%)	n.o	n.o
COD	(0.03;55%)	(0.03;62%)	n.o.	n.o.
PO ₄ ⁻³ -P	(0.04;66%)	n.o	(0.112;57%)	n.o
NO ₃ ⁻ -N	n.o	(0.044;59%)	(0.12;78%)	(0.45;-68%)
NH ₄ ⁺ -N	n.o	(0.01;77%)	n.o	n.o
pH	n.o	(0.001;-75%)	n.o	n.o

n.o. = Spearman correlation was not observed

In Table II can be observed the correlations of Spearman between CH₄ fluxes and water characteristics at the four points. No correlation could be identified between methane flux and the water temperature or the ORP (p>0.05). Positive correlations (p<0.05) were found between methane flux, PO₄⁻³ and COD at P1. By contrast, in P2, DO and pH showed negative correlation whereas COD, NO₃⁻N, NH₄⁺-N, were

correlated positively to the CH₄ emissions. Although in P3 and P4 there were correlations between methane fluxes and PO₄⁻³ (r = 0.57; p = 0.112), and NO₃⁻-N (r = -.68; p = 0.45), it was not significant (p>0.05).

Carbon Dioxide

The CO₂ fluxes for P1, P2, P3, and P4 were 0.9, 0.8, 2.8 and -3.48 g CO₂.m⁻².d⁻¹, respectively (Fig. 3). The statistic comparison between the four points indicated that P4 showed significant differences among P1, P2, and P3 (P1: p = 0.0002; P2: p = 0.0001; P3: p = 0.0001; Mann Whitney test). P4 seems to be a CO₂ sink contributing to carbon sequestration in the FW.

In Table III are shown the correlations of Spearman between CO₂ fluxes and water characteristics at the four points. COD, TP, NO₃⁻-N, and NH₄⁺-N were the most important parameters influencing the CO₂ fluxes from the Sonso Lagoon. At P1, CO₂ fluxes were positively correlated to COD and negatively correlated to NH₄⁺-N (p<0.05). In P2, the concentration measures of TP and NO₃⁻-N (r = 0.89; p = 0.06) showed a positive correlation with CO₂ fluxes (p>0.05). In P2 a negative correlation between NH₄⁺-N and CO₂ release (r = -.55; p = 0.04) was also observed. P3 showed no significant correlation between CO₂ fluxes and the environmental parameters. In P4, the CO₂ fluxes were negatively correlated to the alkalinity (r = -.71; p = 0.05).

Fig. 3 Flux of CO₂ in the Sonso Lagoon

A wide range of GHG emissions are reported in the literature. The mean emissions of CO₂ fluxes in this study were higher than observed in other natural systems [20], [21], [11], [15] but are comparable to values from constructed wetlands treating municipal wastewater [13], [22]. On the other hand, the methane emissions from the Sonso Lagoon were mostly higher than observed in other FWs [20], [21], [11], [15] and comparable to some eco-technological systems for wastewater treatment [13], [22]-[24].

TABLE III
 SPEARMAN CORRELATIONS BETWEEN CO₂ FLUXES AND WATER
 CHARACTERISTICS

Parameter	P1	P2	P3	P4
COD	(0.07; 57%)	n.o.	n.o.	n.o.
TP	n.o.	(0.001; 58%)	n.o.	n.o.
NO ₃ ⁻ -N	n.o.	(0.06; 89%)	n.o.	n.o.
NH ₄ ⁺ -N	(0.04; -62%)	(0.04; -55%)	n.o.	n.o.

n.o. = Spearman correlation was not observed

The results obtained suggest that in general, the Sonso Lagoon was a CH₄ and CO₂ net source. This could be attributed to the eutrophication that suffers this lagoon. In the case of non-anthropogenic intervention, most FWs are net carbon sinks because primary production is often able to sequester more carbon at greater rates than respiration-accreting organic matter into soils over time [25]. However, in natural wetlands that receive wastewater i.e. the Sonso Lagoon, this ability to sequester carbon is affected because the nutrient and organic matter loading enhances mineralization and thus the CH₄ and CO₂ emissions [25], [10], [13], [7], [4].

The variability of CO₂ and CH₄ fluxes in the Sonso Lagoon could not be explained by temperature water changes. This is because all the data were collected during daytime to maximum higher solar radiation and no changes in the water temperature were observed for the different monitoring campaigns.

In this study, the fluxes of CH₄ correlated negatively with both pH and DO and positively with COD at point P2. The organic matter (COD) in P2 enters from sewage and agricultural run-off discharges increasing the oxygen demand. This condition favours anaerobic decomposition in the sediments producing CH₄ that can be released into the atmosphere. In other words more external organic matter and less available oxygen increase CH₄ emissions. The negative correlation between pH and CH₄ fluxes can be explained by the optimum conditions in which the methanogenesis process is carried out, which is between 6.0 and 7.0. In this study, the pH values were higher than 7.0, and thus these conditions indicate that CH₄ production was influenced by this factor.

The presence of PO₄⁻³ and NH₄⁺-N was positively correlated to CH₄ fluxes while apparently NO₃-N decreased CH₄ fluxes. PO₄⁻³ stimulated CH₄ emissions from the Sonso Lagoon, as was reported for lakes and ditches from The Netherlands and Sweden [23], [15]. This is because the increment of PO₄⁻³ in lakes under eutrophication stimulates the transformation of organic matter to methane [10], [26]-[28]. In the same way, the results indicate that an increase in NH₄⁺-N increased CH₄ fluxes from the Sonso Lagoon. This increase can be explained because elevated NH₄⁺-N concentration inhibits CH₄ oxidation [29], [30]. This inhibition is attributed to competition between NH₄⁺-N and CH₄ for binding sites on methane monoxygenase, because of their similar chemical structure [31]. Also the negative correlation between NO₃⁻-N and methane production found in this study has been reported in previous studies [23], [32]. Under anaerobic conditions the organic matter is used by methanogens to produce methane, but at higher NO₃⁻-N concentrations denitrification is favoured

above methanogenesis [12].

Carbon dioxide emissions from the majority of the points in the Sonso Lagoon (P1, P2, P3) were correlated to the NO₃⁻-N, NH₄⁺-N, and TP concentrations. The presence of these nutrients introduces shifts in decomposition rates and nutrient cycling mainly when wetlands become eutrophic. The positive correlation of NH₄⁺-N with CO₂ emission is in line with the findings of wetlands in The Netherlands [15]. Nitrates serve the first terminal electron acceptor in wetland soils after oxygen depletion, making them an important chemical in the oxidation of organic matter in wetlands [33]. Denitrifying bacteria play an important role in the carbon cycle of wetlands as they contribute significantly to the carbon mineralization budget (up to 50%) of the carbon mineralized in eutrophic freshwaters [34]. The positive correlation between TP and CO₂ emissions can be explained by the fact that bacteria depend on phosphorous as a nutrient in the microbial organic matter decomposition [35].

The water characteristics at P1, P2 and P3 were similar, what could be the reason why no significant spatial variations in CH₄ and CO₂ fluxes were observed in the Sonso Lagoon. Only sampling point P4 was significantly different with respect to the CH₄ and CO₂ fluxes. This can be explained because P4 by contrast to P1, P2 and P3 was dominated by floating vegetation such as *Eichhornia crassipes*, *Salvinia* sp., and *Pistia stratiotes* that probably regulated the CH₄ and CO₂ emissions: (i) acting as a physical barrier to prevent the methane diffusion across the water interface into the atmosphere [36], [24], [37]; (ii) sequestering CO₂ by algae and floating plant photosynthesis [25], [38], [22]; and (iii) favouring methane oxidation through translocation of oxygen gaseous produced by photosynthetic activity of the green leaves to the stems and roots and to the water body [39].

The methane fluxes from floating vegetation measured in the Sonso Lagoon (P4) were lower than those reported for emergent macrophytes in other natural wetlands. This suggests that floating plants i.e. *Salvinia* sp have a lower capability to transport CH₄ compared with emergent macrophytes i.e. *Phragmites australis*. This methane-releasing capacity in emergent macrophytes has to do with their continuous access to the atmosphere and their high potential to exchange gases primarily by internal pressurization and convective gas flows [39]-[41]. The superiority of emergent macrophytes compared with floating vegetation with respect to methane emissions was observed in an arid lake area in western China [42] and a southern boreal lake [43]. Likewise, [44] showed that macrophytes, rather than phytoplankton, directly positively affected CH₄. These results and the findings of the current study indicate that species type and areal coverage of the dominating species should be carefully considered when estimating the emissions of CH₄ from wetlands.

Nitrous Oxide

The median N₂O fluxes for P1, P2, P3, and P4 were 0.01, 0.25, 0.19 and -3.19 mg N₂O .m⁻² .d⁻¹, respectively (Fig. 4). The negative median fluxes in P4 indicate that this point acts as a

N₂O sink. At the other points N₂O was emitted. Only P4 showed significant differences compared to P1, P2, and P3.

The N₂O fluxes in the Sonso Lagoon were mostly higher than observed in boreal ponds and FWs [20], [21], [45], [46] and matched with constructed wetlands that receive sewage [47], [13], [32], [22]. The negative fluxes observed in the Sonso Lagoon were also reported for free water surface constructed wetlands [47], [13], [22].

As can be seen in Table IV, the N₂O emissions from P2 were positively correlated to TN and NO₃⁻N. By contrast, in P1, P3, and P4 there were not correlations between N₂O fluxes and the environmental parameters measured.

Fig. 4 Flux of N₂O in the Sonso Lagoon

Total nitrogen and NO₃⁻ influenced the production of N₂O at P1 and P2. This can be explained because N₂O is an intermediate of nitrification and denitrification and its atmospheric release depends on the availability of N (NO₃⁻, NO₂⁻, or NH₄⁺) and oxygen [48], [49]. The presence of N-NO₃, N-NO₂, or N-NH₄⁺ is related to wastewater discharges, sediment exchange from the Cauca River, and agricultural run-off. Nitrifying bacteria may produce NO and N₂O either as a side-product in the catabolic pathway (oxidizing ammonia to nitrite), or, alternatively, denitrifying bacteria may produce NO or N₂O converting nitrite with ammonia, hydrogen or pyruvate as an electron donor [50]-[52].

TABLE IV
SPEARMAN CORRELATIONS BETWEEN N₂O FLUXES AND WATER CHARACTERISTICS

Parameter	P1	P2	P3	P4
TN	n.o.	(0.026;69%)	n.o.	n.o.
NO ₃ ⁻ -N	n.o.	(0.09; 60%)	n.o.	n.o.

n.o. = Spearman correlation was not observed

Nitrous oxide dynamics in wetland plants has been previously described [47], [53], [13], [22]. In the zones with vegetation, N₂O is both emitted and sequestered depending on

the type of vegetation. The presence of vascular plants affects the gas fluxes and leads to significantly higher emissions from most of the vegetated zones [22]. The aerenchymal tissue is more active in the transport of gases from the soil to the atmosphere in vascular plants than in floating plants.

In the current study, it was found that N₂O was taken up in the zone dominated by floating plants and algae and the transport of this gas into the atmosphere was probably limited. This result is in line with the observations in a constructed wetland treating wastewater [54]. The N₂O consumption has also been attributed to NO₃⁻ concentration lower than 0.5 mg.l⁻¹ [54]. This shortage of electron acceptor produces N₂O consumption by denitrifying bacteria. In the Sonso Lagoon, the measurements indicated that NO₃⁻ was around 0.10 mg.l⁻¹ and therefore the emissions of this gas into this atmosphere were decreased. However, it is necessary to elucidate the exact mechanism that affects this N₂O consumption and its relation to other environmental factors and vegetation.

IV. CONCLUSION

The current study focused on GHG emissions from a eutrophic tropical FW located in Colombia. According to the measurements carried out during one year it was possible to conclude that this FW was a net source of CO₂, CH₄, and N₂O. This indicates the impact of anthropogenic activities such as agricultural run-off and wastewater discharges on wetlands switching their ability to sequester C and N to sources of GHGs. Thus, increasing the nutrient loads and input of organic substrates will probably enhance the contribution to global warming of FWs.

ACKNOWLEDGMENT

The authors acknowledges the financial assistance of the National Department for Science, Technology and Innovation (COLCIENCIAS) through project funded by notice No 569 of 2012 "Sequester and capture of greenhouse gases from strategic wetlands in the Valle del Cauca Region".

REFERENCES

- [1] J. B. Zedler and S. Kercher, "Wetland resources: status, trends, ecosystem services, and restorability," *Annu. Rev. Environ. Resour.*, vol. 30, pp. 39-74, 2005.
- [2] W. J. Mitsch and J. G. Gosselink, "Wetlands. Hoboken," ed: John Wiley & Sons, Inc, 2007.
- [3] B. Anderson, K. Bartlett, S. Frolking, K. Hayhoe, J. Jenkins, and W. Salas, "Methane and nitrous oxide emissions from natural sources," *United States Environmental Protection Agency, Office of Atmospheric Programs, Washington*, 2010.
- [4] R. E. Ventura, "Wetlands and Greenhouse Gas Fluxes: Causes and Effects of Climate Change—A Meta-Analysis," 2014.
- [5] P. A. Raymond, J. Hartmann, R. Lauerwald, S. Sobek, C. McDonald, M. Hoover, *et al.*, "Global carbon dioxide emissions from inland waters," *Nature*, vol. 503, pp. 355-359, 2013.
- [6] M. Søndergaard, "Nutrient dynamics in lakes-with emphasis on phosphorus, sediment and lake restoration," Aarhus Universitet Aarhus University, Science and Technology Science and Technology, Institut for Bioscience Department of Bioscience, Institut for Bioscience-Søøkologi Department of Bioscience-Lake Ecology, 2007.
- [7] A. L. Wright, K. Ramesh Reddy, and S. Newman, "Microbial indicators of eutrophication in Everglades wetlands," *Soil Science Society of America Journal*, vol. 73, pp. 1597-1603, 2009.

- [8] P. Casper, S. C. Maberly, G. H. Hall, and B. J. Finlay, "Fluxes of methane and carbon dioxide from a small productive lake to the atmosphere," *Biogeochemistry*, vol. 49, pp. 1-19, 2000.
- [9] J. T. Huttunen, T. Hammar, J. Alm, J. Silvola, and P. J. Martikainen, "Greenhouse gases in non-oxygenated and artificially oxygenated eutrophied lakes during winter stratification," *Journal of environmental quality*, vol. 30, pp. 387-394, 2001.
- [10] J. T. Huttunen, J. Alm, A. Liikanen, S. Juutinen, T. Larmola, T. Hammar, *et al.*, "Fluxes of methane, carbon dioxide and nitrous oxide in boreal lakes and potential anthropogenic effects on the aquatic greenhouse gas emissions," *Chemosphere*, vol. 52, pp. 609-621, 2003.
- [11] Y. Xing, P. Xie, H. Yang, L. Ni, Y. Wang, and K. Rong, "Methane and carbon dioxide fluxes from a shallow hypereutrophic subtropical Lake in China," *Atmospheric Environment*, vol. 39, pp. 5532-5540, 2005.
- [12] J. Stadmark and L. Leonardson, "Emissions of greenhouse gases from ponds constructed for nitrogen removal," *Ecological Engineering*, vol. 25, pp. 542-551, 2005.
- [13] A. Liikanen, J. T. Huttunen, S. M. Karjalainen, K. Heikkinen, T. S. Väisänen, H. Nykänen, *et al.*, "Temporal and seasonal changes in greenhouse gas emissions from a constructed wetland purifying peat mining runoff waters," *Ecological Engineering*, vol. 26, pp. 241-251, 2006.
- [14] H. Wang, L. Yang, W. Wang, J. Lu, and C. Yin, "Nitrous oxide (N₂O) fluxes and their relationships with water-sediment characteristics in a hyper-eutrophic shallow lake, China," *Journal of Geophysical Research: Biogeosciences*, vol. 112, 2007.
- [15] A. Schrier-Uijl, A. Veraart, P. Leffelaar, F. Berendse, and E. Veenendaal, "Release of CO₂ and CH₄ from lakes and drainage ditches in temperate wetlands," *Biogeochemistry*, vol. 102, pp. 265-279, 2011.
- [16] W. E. West, J. J. Coloso, and S. E. Jones, "Effects of algal and terrestrial carbon on methane production rates and methanogen community structure in a temperate lake sediment," *Freshwater Biology*, vol. 57, pp. 949-955, 2012.
- [17] A. a. W. APHA, *Standard methods for the examination of water and wastewater*: American Public Health Association, American Water Works Association and Water Environment Federation, Washington DC, 2005.
- [18] J. P. Silva, A. Lasso, H. J. Lubberding, M. R. Peña, and H. J. Gijzen, "Biases in greenhouse gases static chambers measurements in stabilization ponds: Comparison of flux estimation using linear and non-linear models," *Atmospheric Environment*, vol. 109, pp. 130-138, 2015.
- [19] D. V. Chapman, W. H. Organization, and C. Press, *Water quality assessments: a guide to the use of biota, sediments and water in environmental monitoring*: E & Fn Spon London, 1996.
- [20] J. T. Huttunen, T. S. Väisänen, M. Heikkinen, S. Hellsten, H. Nykänen, O. Nenonen, *et al.*, "Exchange of CO₂, CH₄ and N₂O between the atmosphere and two northern boreal ponds with catchments dominated by peatlands or forests," *Plant and soil*, vol. 242, pp. 137-146, 2002.
- [21] A. Tremblay, M. Lambert, and L. Gagnon, "Do hydroelectric reservoirs emit greenhouse gases?," *Environmental Management*, vol. 33, pp. S509-S517, 2004.
- [22] L. Ström, A. Lamppa, and T. R. Christensen, "Greenhouse gas emissions from a constructed wetland in southern Sweden," *Wetlands Ecology and Management*, vol. 15, pp. 43-50, 2007.
- [23] A. Johansson, A.-M. Gustavsson, M. Öquist, and B. Svensson, "Methane emissions from a constructed wetland treating wastewater—seasonal and spatial distribution and dependence on edaphic factors," *Water research*, vol. 38, pp. 3960-3970, 2004.
- [24] J. P. Silva, J. L. Ruiz, M. R. Peña, H. Lubberding, and H. Gijzen, "Influence of photoperiod on carbon dioxide and methane emissions from two pilot-scale stabilization ponds," *Water Science & Technology*, vol. 66, 2012.
- [25] H. Brix, B. K. Sorrell, and B. Lorenzen, "Are Phragmites-dominated wetlands a net source or net sink of greenhouse gases?," *Aquatic Botany*, vol. 69, pp. 313-324, 2001.
- [26] T. Adhya, P. Pattnaik, S. Satpathy, S. Kumaraswamy, and N. Sethunathan, "Influence of phosphorus application on methane emission and production in flooded paddy soils," *Soil Biology and Biochemistry*, vol. 30, pp. 177-181, 1998.
- [27] R. Conrad and M. Klose, "Effect of potassium phosphate fertilization on production and emission of methane and its 13 C-stable isotope composition in rice microcosms," *Soil Biology and Biochemistry*, vol. 37, pp. 2099-2108, 2005.
- [28] Q.-Q. Sun, K. Shi, P. Damerell, C. Whitham, G.-H. Yu, and C.-L. Zou, "Carbon dioxide and methane fluxes: seasonal dynamics from inland riparian ecosystems, northeast China," *Science of the total environment*, vol. 465, pp. 48-55, 2013.
- [29] H. Biswas, S. Mukhopadhyay, S. Sen, and T. Jana, "Spatial and temporal patterns of methane dynamics in the tropical mangrove dominated estuary, NE coast of Bay of Bengal, India," *Journal of Marine Systems*, vol. 68, pp. 55-64, 2007.
- [30] G. Borrel, D. Jézéquel, C. Biderre-Petit, N. Morel-Desrosiers, J.-P. Morel, P. Peyret, *et al.*, "Production and consumption of methane in freshwater lake ecosystems," *Research in Microbiology*, vol. 162, pp. 832-847, 2011.
- [31] C. Bédard and R. Knowles, "Physiology, biochemistry, and specific inhibitors of CH₄, NH₄⁺, and CO oxidation by methanotrophs and nitrifiers," *Microbiological reviews*, vol. 53, pp. 68-84, 1989.
- [32] A. Søvik and B. Kløve, "Emission of N₂O and CH₄ from a constructed wetland in southeastern Norway," *Science of the Total Environment*, vol. 380, pp. 28-37, 2007.
- [33] S. Sánchez-Carrillo, D. Angeler, M. Álvarez-Cobelas, and R. Sánchez-Andrés, "Freshwater wetland eutrophication," in *Eutrophication: causes, consequences and control*, ed: Springer, 2011, pp. 195-210.
- [34] P. B. Christensen, L. P. Nielsen, J. Sørensen, and N. P. Revsbech, "Denitrification in nitrate-rich streams: diurnal and seasonal variation related to benthic oxygen metabolism," *Limnology and Oceanography*, vol. 35, pp. 640-651, 1990.
- [35] A. L. Wright, K. R. Reddy, and S. Newman, "Biogeochemical response of the Everglades landscape to eutrophication," *Global J Environ Res*, vol. 2, pp. 102-109, 2008.
- [36] N. Van der Steen, A. Ferrer, K. Samarasinghe, H. Gijzen, and I. W. Association, "Quantification and comparison of methane emissions from algae and duckweed based wastewater treatment ponds," in *Memorias del evento: Agua 2003*, ed: IWA, 2003, pp. 1-7.
- [37] N. P. Van der Steen, A. V. M. Ferrer, K. G. Samarasinghe, and H. J. Gijzen, "Quantification and comparison of methane emissions from algae and duckweed based wastewater treatment ponds," *Universidad del Valle; CINARA: International Water Association. Memorias del evento: Agua 2003. Cartagena de Indias, IWA, 2003, p. 1-7 Ilus.*, 2003.
- [38] S. Teiter and Ü. Mander, "Emission of N₂O, N₂, CH₄, and CO₂ from constructed wetlands for wastewater treatment and from riparian buffer zones," *Ecological Engineering*, vol. 25, pp. 528-541, 2005.
- [39] H. J. Laanbroek, "Methane emission from natural wetlands: interplay emergent macrophytes and soil microbial processes. A mini-review," *Annals of Botany*, vol. 105, pp. 141-153, 2010.
- [40] H. Brix, B. K. Sorrell, and H.-H. Schierup, "Gas fluxes achieved by in situ convective flow in Phragmites australis," *Aquatic Botany*, vol. 54, pp. 151-163, 1996.
- [41] B. Sorrell and H. Brix, "Effects of water vapour pressure deficit and stomatal conductance on photosynthesis, internal pressurization and convective flow in three emergent wetland plants," *Plant and Soil*, vol. 253, pp. 71-79, 2003.
- [42] X. Duan, X. Wang, Y. Mu, and Z. Ouyang, "Seasonal and diurnal variations in methane emissions from Wuliangsu Lake in arid regions of China," *Atmospheric Environment*, vol. 39, pp. 4479-4487, 2005.
- [43] I. Bergström, S. Mäkelä, P. Kankaala, and P. Kortelainen, "Methane efflux from littoral vegetation stands of southern boreal lakes: an upscaled regional estimate," *Atmospheric Environment*, vol. 41, pp. 339-351, 2007.
- [44] Y. Xing, P. Xie, H. Yang, A. Wu, and L. Ni, "The change of gaseous carbon fluxes following the switch of dominant producers from macrophytes to algae in a shallow subtropical lake of China," *Atmospheric Environment*, vol. 40, pp. 8034-8043, 2006.
- [45] C. Song, L. Zhang, Y. Wang, and Z. Zhao, "Annual dynamics of CO₂, CH₄, N₂O emissions from freshwater marshes and affected by nitrogen fertilization," *Huan jing ke xue= Huanjing kexue/bian ji, Zhongguo ke xue yuan huan jing ke xue wei yuan hui" Huan jing ke xue" bian ji wei yuan hui.*, vol. 27, p. 2369, 2006.
- [46] J. Yang, J. Liu, X. Hu, X. Li, Y. Wang, and H. Li, "Effect of water table level on CO₂, CH₄ and N₂O emissions in a freshwater marsh of Northeast China," *Soil Biology and Biochemistry*, vol. 61, pp. 52-60, 2013.
- [47] A. Johansson, Å. K. Klemedtsson, L. Klemedtsson, and B. Svensson, "Nitrous oxide exchanges with the atmosphere of a constructed wetland treating wastewater," *Tellus B*, vol. 55, pp. 737-750, 2003.
- [48] P. M. Groffman, J. Rogers, and W. Whitman, "Ecology of nitrification and denitrification in soil evaluated at scales relevant to atmospheric

- chemistry," *Microbial production and consumption of greenhouse gases: methane, nitrogen oxides, and halomethanes.*, pp. 201-217, 1991.
- [49] J. T. Morris, "Effects of nitrogen loading on wetland ecosystems with particular reference to atmospheric deposition," *Annual Review of Ecology and Systematics*, vol. 22, pp. 257-279, 1991.
- [50] B. Colliver and T. Stephenson, "Production of nitrogen oxide and dinitrogen oxide by autotrophic nitrifiers," *Biotechnology advances*, vol. 18, pp. 219-232, 2000.
- [51] N. Wrage, G. Velthof, M. Van Beusichem, and O. Oenema, "Role of nitrifier denitrification in the production of nitrous oxide," *Soil biology and Biochemistry*, vol. 33, pp. 1723-1732, 2001.
- [52] Y. Law, L. Ye, Y. Pan, and Z. Yuan, "Nitrous oxide emissions from wastewater treatment processes," *Phil. Trans. R. Soc. B*, vol. 367, pp. 1265-1277, 2012.
- [53] M. E. Hernandez and W. J. Mitsch, "Influence of hydrologic pulses, flooding frequency, and vegetation on nitrous oxide emissions from created riparian marshes," *Wetlands*, vol. 26, pp. 862-877, 2006.
- [54] A. E. Johansson, A. K. Klemedtsson, L. Klemedtsson, and B. H. Svensson, "Nitrous oxide exchanges with the atmosphere of a constructed wetland treating wastewater. Parameters and implications for emission factors," *Tellus B*, vol. 55, pp. 737-750, 2003.